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Effect of acidity on seed germination of selected varieties of paddy

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Abstract

Emissions caused by burning of fossil fuels have tremendously increased acid deposition on earth in the form of sulphuric and nitric acids along with rain, fog, mist and snow badly affecting agricultural harvests. Although similar conditions have not been reported from Sri Lanka its occurrence could be anticipated with increasing rate of urbanization and changes in the climate. In this research we hypothesized that exposure to “acid rain” could affect seed germination of direct seeded paddy, impacting on rice production, the staple food of Asian communities. We recorded final germination percentage of 03 traditional (*Ranthawalu* (RT), *Herathbanda* (HB), *Suwandel* (SD) and 03 improved paddy (*Oriza sativa*) varieties (BW -367, BW – 372, BW - 272-6b) in an acidic medium (pH 2 to pH4) prepared using sulphuric acid and distilled water. The control had distilled water. The experiment was conducted using sterile petri plates lined with filter paper using 25 replicates each containing 100 seeds for each variety. The Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) at $P < 0.05$ revealed that seed germination of traditional RT, and improved varieties were affected when they were exposed to an acidic medium while the traditional varieties HB and SD did not. Hence it can be concluded that seeds of traditional rice varieties HB and SD possess the capacity to strengthen food security in Sri Lanka under potential conditions of ‘acid rain’ in the future.

INTRODUCTION

Pollution is a topic widely discussed throughout the world. One of the ways “Pollutants” impact on life on earth is through acid rains. ‘Acid rains’ make rain water acidic due to increased emissions SO₂ and NO_x released to air by intense burning of fossil fuels by human beings. Sulphuric and Nitric acids contaminated with rain water have changed the pH of rain water making it less than pH 4.

Agriculture is one sector badly affected due to acid rains. Crop damage threatens food security elsewhere. Rice is a major crop especially cultivated in highly populated countries in Asia. It is staple food of Sri Lankans from ancient times. Rice is grown in almost all soil types of Sri Lanka, accommodating 1/3 of the total cultivated land area of the country. About 1.8 million families are engaged in paddy cultivation in Sri Lanka. To reduce human labour and maintenance costs, rice is grown as a rain – fed crop directly sown in paddy fields in our country.

If there will be acid rains reported in Sri Lanka in the near future rice will be one major crop that will be seriously affected. So it is important to study how rice plants could germinate under acidic conditions. The information is also very important in developing disaster preparedness plan to strengthen food security of Sri Lanka.

‘Rice’ varieties are often referred as ‘paddy varieties’ in local language, so hereafter we use the word ‘paddy’.

Research Questions

Are there any paddy varieties in Sri Lanka that will tolerate acidic conditions and germinate successfully in an acidic medium (similar to that represented by acid rains)?

AIM

Our objective was to identify suitable paddy varieties that will successfully germinate in an acidic medium, which will be more or less similar to that of the acid rain

HYPOTHESIS

In this study we hypothesized that acidic conditions are harmful to complete the germination process of Sri Lankan paddy varieties.

1. MATERIALS AND METHOD

- 1kg of each variety of paddy seeds of BW – 367, BW – 372, BW – 272-6b, *Ranthawalu*, *Herathbanda*, and *Suwandel* that certified by the Regional Rice Research center of the Department of Agriculture in Sri Lanka.
- Distilled water (about 7 litres)
- 600 Sterilized petri plates
- Few Large beakers
- Sterilized Filter papers
- 2l of each Acidic solution of pH2, pH3, pH4 prepared using 98% H₂SO₄
- Six small basins.

Selection of paddy varieties for the experiment

On recommendation of the Department of Agriculture, three traditional [*Ranthawalu* (RT), *Herathbanda* (HB), *Suwandel* (SD)] and three improved varieties [BW – 367, BW – 372, BW - 272-bb] of paddy which is being heavily used by farmers were chosen for the experiment. The seeds were supplied by the Regional Rice Research center of the Department of Agriculture.

Testing the effect of acidic solutions on germination of paddy seeds

Laboratory facilities were provided by the Regional Rice Research and Development Center at Bombuwela of the Department of Agriculture. Firstly, the germination capacity of seed samples of the six varieties were tested using sterile petri plates lined with filter paper and moistened with distilled water. A series of acidic solutions were made by mixing Sulphuric acid with distilled water and the pH was separately adjusted to be 2, 3, 4. Germination experiment was conducted using 25 replicates each containing 100 seeds for each variety for each pH condition. Hence a total of 2400 seeds from each variety on filter paper in petri plates were exposed separately to with equal amounts of pH 2, 3 and 4 solutions. Germination was considered as the emergence of the radicle. Seed germination of paddy varieties was monitored and the final germination percentage was calculated and analyzed at each pH level using Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) at P<0.05 level of significance using the Minitab software package.

Handling Risk and safety

The experiment was conducted adhering to the laboratory guidelines to minimize the risks and maximize safety. Safety measures for handling acid solutions (Sulphuric acid) included wearing lab-coat, gloves and protective eyewear (goggles), avoiding spilling solutions on the working bench, wiping up as much of the spilled material with paper towels and disposing them properly to the bin provided in the laboratory, and washing hands thoroughly with soap and warm water before leaving the lab.

2. RESULTS

When paddy seeds were exposed to distilled water all varieties showed a very high final germination percentage above 95%. The effect of the acidic medium on seed germination was very clear as final germination percentage of different paddy varieties were changed.

According to ANOVA *Suwandel* and *Herathbanda* paddy varieties did not show significant difference in germination in pH 2, pH3, pH4 acidic medium compared to the control (distilled water).

Figure 1. Normal germination percentage of the six paddy varieties

Sample	Germination Percentage					
	BW 367	BW 372	BW 272- 6b	Ranthawalu	Herathband	Suwadel
S1	95%	98%	99%	96%	98%	98%
S2	94%	98%	100%	96%	99%	97%
S3	98%	98%	100%	96%	99%	98%
Average	96%	98%	100%	96%	99%	98%

Table 1. Final seed germination percentage of paddy varieties at varying pH. Values indicate average of 25 replicates.

Final germination percentage of paddy seeds				
Paddy variety	pH2	pH3	pH4	Control
<i>Herathbanda</i> (HB)	59.24	72.20	85.00	92.96
<i>Ranthawalu</i> (RT)	28.29	71.70	84.85	97.60
<i>Suwandel</i> (SD)	80.72	93.60	96.24	97.20
BW 367	0.63	28.00	76.60	95.00
BW 372	1.22	50.00	70.80	96.00
BW 272- 6b	12.64	50.36	75.54	97.00

Figure 2. ANOVA test result

Sprouting Percentage Vs pH

BW 367

Sprouting Percentage Vs pH

BW- 372

Sprouting Percentage Vs pH

BW 272-6B

3. DISCUSSION

It is essential to identify the germination and growth responses of paddy varieties of Sri Lanka to successfully meet the challenges of possible acid rain situations. Seed germination stage is a critical stage of a life cycle of a plant. There is an urgent need to identify suitable paddy varieties that could be able to germinate in acidic medium if acid rains will be reported in Sri Lanka in the near future. This is an important aspect which could be included in the disaster preparedness plans to protect rice production in the country. If Sri Lanka encounters with such conditions farmers could be encouraged to growth paddy varieties which will not be affected due to the acidic conditions of the environment.

This study identified that seed germination of *Ranthawalu* and improved varieties (Bw 367, Bw 372, Bw 272 – 6b) were badly affected when they are grown in an acidic medium while the traditional varieties *Herathbanda* and *Suwandel* was not affected. The reason for the inhibition in germination by the acidic medium could be due to the direct effect on acids on enzyme actions.

ASSUMPTIONS

All acid solutions (pH 2, pH3, and pH4) were prepared using H₂SO₄. The acidity of a solution is expressed by amount of (H⁺) ions of the solution and acidity of the acid rain is expressed by pH value. So it was assumed that acidic medium reflected the same condition similar to acidity resulted due to an acid rain.

4. CONCLUSION

Paddy varieties did not germinate in the same way when they were exposed to acidic conditions. Germination of some paddy varieties were badly affected when they were exposed to acidic medium similar to that of acid rains while traditional paddy varieties *Suwndel* and *Herathbanda* were capable in germinating in the acidic medium.

5. SUGGESTIONS

- It is essential to identify the paddy varieties which are eligible against with the acid rains and to produce a greater harvest.
- It is needed to anew produce improved hybrid paddy varieties which can be sustainable to acid rains and can be used to make a greater harvest.
- Currently, the acidity of the rain water is not measured in Sri Lanka and the necessity of measuring the acidity of rain water is essentially stressed. It can be done along with the measuring of rainfall by the agricultural and meteorological institutions. This emphasis is recommended to consider for the other countries in the world which do not measure the acidity of the rain water along with the rainfall.
- It is found that the germination of seeds of paddy can be affected by acid rains and there is an important needs of improving the awareness of the countries of Asia about the findings. It would become helpful to be in alert on the risk and to be observant for the precautions since the rice is one of the major staple food in Asia.
- If Sri Lanka encounters with acid rains , the country will be able to overcome that problematic challenge of producing a sufficient harvest of rice as some paddy varieties like *Suvandal* , and *Herath Banda* have been already recognized by us since such varieties are sustainable against with acid rains.
- Although the predictable risk of a food crisis due to acid rains is pre - identified, the world does not take regulation and measures to avoid fossil fuel since it is solicited to call for a fall of technological thrive of the world. In these situations, moving for sustainable paddy varieties under acid rain status would be a promising way of producing the expected food harvest for the world's people. Therefore we keep ourselves to be hopeful on the countries to be aware about these research findings.
- This knowledge can be expanded beyond the paddy cultivation and the countries could be encouraged to identify, anew produce or improve varieties of other crops which are sustainable under the acid rain effects.

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7. Continuation Sheet

1. Classification of rice

Oryza sativa

Scientific classification

Kingdom: **Plantae**
Clade: **Angiosperms**
Clade: **Monocots**
Clade: **Commelinids**
Order: **Poales**
Family: **Poaceae**
Genus: ***Oryza***
Species: ***O. sativa***

Binomial name

Oryza sativa
L.

Food consumption of rice by country – 2009
(million metric ton of paddy equivalent)^[107]

World Total	531.6
China	156.3
India	123.5
Bangladesh	50.4
Indonesia	45.3
Vietnam	18.4
Philippines	17.0
Thailand	13.7
Japan	10.2
Burma	10.0
Brazil	10.0
South Korea	5.8
Nigeria	4.8
Egypt	4.6
Pakistan	4.3
United States	3.8
Nepal	3.5
Cambodia	3.4
Sri Lanka	3.2
Madagascar	3.2
Malaysia	3.1
North Korea	2.8

Rice production – 2016

Country	Production (millions of tonnes)
China	209.5
India	158.8
Indonesia	77.3
Bangladesh	52.6
Vietnam	43.4
Myanmar	25.7
Thailand	25.3
World	741.0

Source: FAOSTAT of the United Nations^[1]